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Two new species of *Diostracus* Loew, 1861 (Diptera: Dolichopodidae) from the Caucasus with a key to species from the region

© I.Ya. Grichanov¹, B.I. Volfov^{2,3}

¹All-Russian Institute of Plant Protection, Podbelskiy Roadway, 3, St Petersburg, Pushkin 196608 Russia. E-mail: grichanov@mail.ru

²Ministry of Natural Resources of Krasnodarskiy Region, Severnaya Street, 275/1, Krasnodar 350020 Russia. E-mail: borisvolfov@yandex.ru

³Kuban State University, Stavropol'skaya Street, 149, Krasnodar 350040 Russia

Abstract. *Diostracus khevsureticus* sp. n. from highlands of Georgia and *D. osseticus* sp. n. from highlands of South Ossetia are described and illustrated and associated with the subgenus *Lagodechia* Negrobov et Tsurikov, 1996, comprising now three Caucasian species and three species from Oriental China. *Diostracus kustovi* Grichanov, 2013 is firstly recorded from Georgia. A key to five *Diostracus* Loew, 1861 species known from the Caucasus is provided.

Key words: long-legged flies, Palaearctic region, Georgia, South Ossetia, *Diostracus*, new species.

Два новых вида рода *Diostracus* Loew, 1861 (Diptera: Dolichopodidae) с Кавказа с определителем видов региона

© И.Я. Гричанов¹, Б.И. Вольфов^{2,3}

¹Всероссийский институт защиты растений, шоссе Подбельского, 3, Санкт-Петербург, Пушкин 196608 Россия. E-mail: grichanov@mail.ru

²Министерство природных ресурсов Краснодарского края, ул. Северная, 275/1, Краснодар, 350020 Россия. E-mail: borisvolfov@yandex.ru

³Кубанский государственный университет, ул. Ставропольская, 149, Краснодар 350040 Россия

Резюме. Описаны и иллюстрированы *Diostracus khevsureticus* sp. n. из высокогорий Грузии и *D. osseticus* sp. n. из высокогорий Южной Осетии. Они помещены в подрод *Lagodechia* Negrobov et Tsurikov, 1996, в который теперь входят три кавказских вида и три вида из Ориентального Китая. *Diostracus kustovi* Grichanov, 2013 впервые указывается для Грузии. Составлен определитель пяти видов рода *Diostracus* Loew, 1861, известных на Кавказе.

Ключевые слова: мухи-зеленушки, Палеарктика, Грузия, Южная Осетия, *Diostracus*, новые виды.

Introduction

The genus *Diostracus* Loew, 1861 is known by 110 species described from the Palaearctic, Oriental and Nearctic regions, but with rich diversity in highlands of the Himalayas and Tibetan Plateau. It was reviewed by Yang et al. [2011] for the Chinese fauna, Grichanov [2013] for the West Palaearctic fauna, and Wang et al. [2015] for the Himalayan fauna. Later Pusch [2015] described *D. lemavajulorum* from Corsica (France), and Zhu et al. [2023] described six new species of *Diostracus* from Tibet (China). In the East Palaearctic fauna, *Diostracus* is known also from Russia (Republic of Buryatia, Primorskiy Region, Sakhalin), Japan and Korea [Grichanov, 2024]. Almost all species are endemic to mountainous countries or maritime territories. With the new species described here, the Palaearctic fauna of *Diostracus* now totals 34 species including five species inhabiting the Caucasus.

Material and methods

The types of two new species are housed at the Zoological Institute of the Russian Academy of Sciences (ZIN, St Petersburg, Russia). Specimens have been studied and photographed with a ZEISS SteREO Discovery.V12 microscope and an AxioCam MRc5 camera. Morphological terminology and abbreviations follow Cumming and Wood [2017] and Grichanov and Brooks [2017]. The lengths of

the antennomeres and podomeres are given in millimetres. Body length is measured from the base of the antenna to the tip of the abdominal segment 6. Wing length is measured from the base to the wing apex. Antenna length is measured from the base of the scape to tip of the arista-like stylus. The figures showing the hypopygium in lateral view are oriented as it appears on the intact specimens. Line drawings of the hypopygium are not provided, because they cannot show correctly the shape of appendages in lateral view; instead, the micrographs of hypandrium, phallus, epandrial lobe, surstylus and cercus from various aspects are given.

Genus *Diostracus* Loew, 1861

Diostracus Loew, 1861: 43 (type species *Diostracus prasinus* Loew, 1861, by monotypy).

Notes. See Grichanov [2013] for diagnosis of the genus *Diostracus* and Pusch [2015] for a review of ecological preferences of species. Grichanov [2013] recognised two subgenera of the genus in the Caucasus, i.e. *Sphyrotarsus* Miik, 1874, and *Lagodechia* Negrobov et Tsurikov, 1996. *Diostracus* (*L.*) *spinulifer* Negrobov et Tsurikov, 1988 is known from Georgia; *D. (S.) caucasicus* (Negrobov, 1965) inhabits Adygea and Krasnodar Region (Russia); *D. (S.) kustovi* Grichanov, 2013 has been described from Karachay-Cherkessia of Russia, being reported here from Georgia. Two new species of the genus are described and illustrated below. *Diostracus khevsureticus* sp. n. from Georgia and *D. osseticus* sp. n. from South Ossetia are

associated here with the subgenus *Lagodechia*. At present, three more species of this subgenus are known from Oriental China (Yunnan, Guizhou, Hunan and Sichuan) [Grichanov, 2017].

Key to *Diostracus* species (males) from the Caucasus

1. Scutellum with 1–2 pairs of long bristles and with some short lateral setae or hairs (subgenus *Lagodechia*) 2
- Scutellum with 3 pairs of almost equally long bristles (subgenus *Sphyrotarsus*) 4
2. Sterna 2–4 of abdomen without strong setae, with short white hairs; fore basitarsus with 5 short ventral hooked setae in basal half (Fig. 4); body 4.9 mm long *D. khevsureticus* sp. n.
- Sterna 2–4 of abdomen each with groups of strong setae; fore basitarsus with ventral row of 15–20 very short blunt setae in middle half (Fig. 15) 3
3. Wing cross-vein dm-m more than 2 times as long as distal part of M_4 ; hind basitarsus with 3 long light posterodorsal setae at base, nearly half as long as basitarsus; body 5–6.5 mm long *D. spinulifer*
- Wing cross-vein dm-m about 1.5 times as long as distal part of M_4 ; hind basitarsus without long setae; body 6.5 mm long *D. osseticus* sp. n.
4. Sterna 2 and 3 of abdomen each with strong black spines; body 9.4 mm long *D. kustovi*
- Male abdominal sternites without strong spines; body 6 mm long *D. caucasicus*

Figs 1–5. *Diostracus (Lagodechia) khevsureticus* sp. n., male, holotype.

1 – habitus, lateral view; 2 – head, anterior view; 3 – left antenna, outer lateral view; 4 – fore femur, tibia and basitarsus, posterior view; 5 – fore tarsomeres 3–5, ventral view.

Рис. 1–5. *Diostracus (Lagodechia) khevsureticus* sp. n., самец, голотип.

1 – внешний вид, сбоку; 2 – голова, спереди; 3 – левый усик, снаружи сбоку; 4 – передние бедро, голень и базитарзус, сзади; 5 – 3–5-й членики передней лапки, снизу.

Diostracus (Lagodechia) khevsureticus sp. n.
(Figs 1–10)

Material. Holotype, ♂ (ZIN): Georgia, Mtskheta-Mtianeti Region, Dusheti Municipality, Khevsureti, Greater Caucasus Range, SW slope of Tanie Mt [42.38°N / 45.00°E], 2850 m, 19.07.2014 (D.A. Zhrebilo) (in Russian Cyrillic).

Diagnosis. According to Grichanov [2013], the new species belongs to the subgenus *Lagodechia*, which differs from other subgenera in the absence of dorsal setae on antennal scape, presence of one or two pairs of long bristles on scutellum, short postpedicel with dorsal stylus. *Diostracus khevsureticus* sp. n. differs from males of other two Caucasian species of the subgenus in the absence of strong setae on the abdominal sterna 2–4 that have only short white hairs; male fore basitarsus bears five short ventral hooked setae in its basal half. *Diostracus spinulifer* and *D. osseticus* sp. n. males are somewhat larger, bear

groups of strong setae on sterna 2–4 of the abdomen and ventral row of 15–20 very short blunt setae in the middle half of fore basitarsus.

Description. Male (Fig. 1). Length (mm): body without antennae 4.9, antenna 1.1, wing 5.6/1.8. Head (Fig. 2): black, grey pollinose; clypeus shining, 1/3 as wide as head, 1.6 times as wide as high; face nearly as wide as clypeus, 1.6 times as wide as height of postpedicel; ocellar bristles strong, vertical bristle short; postvertical bristle slightly longer than upper postocular bristle; about 10 upper postocular setae black, strong, finer and whitish below; ventral 1/2 of postcranium clothed with many long white hairs; antenna (Fig. 3) black, with glabrous vase-like scape; pedicel with ring of short setae; postpedicel as long as high, rounded distally, with short hairs, with dorsoapical simple arista-like stylus; basal segment of stylus thickened; length (mm) of scape, pedicel, postpedicel, arista-like stylus (aristomeres 1 and 2), 0.14 : 0.08 : 0.18 : 0.11 : 0.68; palpus ovate, 1.5 times as long as wide, 1/3 as long as eye height, slightly dilated at middle; palpus brown, silvery white pollinose, bearing black hairs and setae; proboscis moderately large, brown.

Figs 6–10. *Diostracus (Lagodechia) khevsureticus* sp. n., male, holotype. 6 – segments 3–5 and 8 of abdomen and hypopygium, ventral view; 7 – hypopygium, right lateral view; 8 – hypandrium, phallus and surstylus, lateral view; 9 – surstylus, ventral view; 10 – cercus, lateral view. Abbreviations: cer – cercus; hyp – hypandrium; ph – phallus; sur – surstylus.

Рис. 6–10. *Diostracus (Lagodechia) khevsureticus* sp. n., самец, голотип.

6 – сегменты 3–5 и 8 брюшка и гипопигий, снизу; 7 – гипопигий, справа сбоку; 8 – гипандрий, фаллус и сурстиль, сбоку; 9 – сурстиль, снизу; 10 – церка, сбоку. Сокращения: cer – церка; hyp – гипандрий; ph – фаллус; sur – сурстиль.

Thorax: greenish black, with grey pollinosity; mesonotum with pair of blackish longitudinal stripes; acrostichals absent; 7 pairs of dorsocentrals; 2 humeral setae, 1 posthumeral, 2 notopleurals, 1 sutural, 1 postsutural, 1 supra-alar, 1 postalar; scutellum with 2 pairs of strong scutellars; proepisternum with 7–8 white hairs on its upper portion and 7–8 white setae on its lower portion; scutellum about 3 times wider than long; postscutellum about 3 times as long as scutellum.

Legs: rather long, black, with black major setae; fore coxa on anterior surface with long white hairs, with 6 short black apical setae; fore femur (Fig. 4) simple, moderately thick in basal half, with irregular posteroventral row of 12–14 setae in distal half, shorter than femur height; fore tibia slightly thickened, bearing 2 anterodorsal, 2 posterodorsal bristles in basal 1/3, 1 strong dorsal bristle at 2/3, 2 ventral rows of short erect black setae, 1 long apical seta; fore basitarsus long, covered with semi-erect black setulae, with 5 short ventral hooked setae in basal half (Fig. 5); tarsomeres 2–4 simple, bearing semi-erect black setulae, ventrally bare; tarsomere 4 with pair of apicoventral setae; tarsomere 5 elongated; pulvilli not reduced, but small, empodium well developed and ventrally ciliated, claws about half as long as tarsomere 5; mid coxa bearing long white hairs; mid femur simple, with setulae only; mid tibia straight, with 3 anterodorsal and 2 posterodorsal bristles and 5 short apical setae; mid tarsus

slender, simple; tarsomere 4 with pair of apicoventral setae; tarsomere 5 with small claws, pulvilli and empodium; hind coxa bearing short white seta at apex; hind femur long and simple, with anterior preapical bristle; hind tibia slender, bearing 3 anterodorsal and 4 posterodorsal bristles and 5 short apical setae, short setae on ventral surface; hind tarsus slender and simple; tarsomere 4 with pair of apicoventral setae; claws, pulvilli and empodium small. Femur, tibia and tarsomere (from first to fifth) length (mm): fore leg: 1.57 : 1.43 : 0.75 : 0.35 : 0.26 : 0.16 : 0.27; mid leg: 1.98 : 2.12 : 1.05 : 0.32 : 0.25 : 0.16 : 0.34; hind leg: 2.37 : 2.49 : 0.89 : 0.48 : 0.34 : 0.19 : 0.26.

Wing (Fig. 1): long and narrow, evenly greyish, with black veins; Sc developed; C slightly thickened behind R_1 ; R_{2+3} and R_{4+5} weakly convex anteriorly, almost parallel in middle half of wing, then divergent distally; R_{4+5} and M_{1+2} almost parallel at wing apex; M_{1+2} almost straight; ratio of part of costa between R_{2+3} and R_{4+5} to this between R_{4+5} and M_{1+2} , 0.65 : 0.35; ratio of cross-vein dm-m to distal part of M_4 , 0.62 : 0.39; dm-m almost perpendicular to longitudinal wing axis; calypter brownish, with white cilia; halter brownish yellow with brown knob.

Abdomen (Fig. 6): greenish black, with grey pollinosity, with short black setae; terga with black hairs; sterna normal, with short white hairs; sternum 4 with small median distal tubercle; sternum 5 divided into 2 sclerites, each with small distal

Figs 11–16. *Diostracus (Lagodechia) osseticus* sp. n., male, paratype.

11 – habitus, lateral view; 12 – head, anterior view; 13 – left antenna, outer lateral view; 14 – fore tibia, anterior view; 15 – fore basitarsus, posterior view, with arrow showing blunt setae; 16 – abdomen, lateral view.

Рис. 11–16. *Diostracus (Lagodechia) osseticus* sp. n., самец, паратип.

11 – внешний вид, сбоку; 12 – голова, спереди; 13 – левый усик, снаружи сбоку; 14 – передняя голень, спереди; 15 – передний базитарзус, сзади (стрелка показывает тупоконечные щетинки); 16 – брюшко, сбоку.

tubercle; tergum 6 small, shortly setose; tergum 7 reduced to semicircular arc, with some short setae; segment 8 large, covered with black hairs; hypopygium (Fig. 7) black, moderately large, with black appendages; hypandrium (Fig. 8) elongated, flat, widened at apex, with distal emargination (ventral view); phallus simple; epandrial lobe (Fig. 9) short, finger-like; dorsal and ventral lobes of surstylus thick, fused at base; dorsal lobe of surstylus with 5 short setae; ventral lobe of surstylus with 3 long setae; cercus (Fig. 10) black, 2/3 length of epandrium, elongate-ovate, with long yellow setae.

Female unknown.

Distribution. Georgia.

Etymology. The species is named after the type locality, a historical-ethnographic region Khevsureti in eastern Georgia.

Note. The new species was collected together with males and females *Diostracus kustovi*, originally described (in the subgenus *Sphyrotarsus*) from the Karachay-Cherkessia Republic of Russia (Sofyiskie waterfalls).

Diostracus (Lagodechia) osseticus sp. n.
(Figs 11–20)

Material. Holotype, ♂ (ZIN): Central Caucasus, South Ossetia, Gudisskiy Range, Britatdon River head, N slopes of Mangavtsek Mt [42.38°N / 45.00°E], 2700 m, 21.07.2013 (D.A. Zhrebilo) (in Russian Cyrillic). Paratype: 1♂ (ZIN), same data as for the holotype.

Diagnosis. According to Grichanov [2013], the new species belongs to the subgenus *Lagodechia*, being very

Figs 17–20. *Diostracus (Lagodechia) osseticus* sp. n., male, paratype. 17 – segments 3–5 and 8 of abdomen and hypopygium, lateral view; 18 – segment 5 of abdomen, ventral view; 19 – hypandrium, phallus and epandrial lobe, lateral view; 20 – surstylus (partly obscured), lateral view. Abbreviations: tg – tergite; st – sternite; epl – epandrial lobe; hyp – hypandrium; ph – phallus.

Рис. 17–20. *Diostracus (Lagodechia) osseticus* sp. n., самец, паратип.

17 – сегменты 3–5 и 8 брюшка и гипопигий, сбоку; 18 – 5-й сегмент брюшка, снизу; 19 – гипандрий, фаллус и лопасть эпандрия, сбоку; 20 – сурстиль (частично скрыт), сбоку. Сокращения: tg – тергит; st – стернит; epl – лопасть эпандрия; hyp – гипандрий; ph – фаллус.

close in habitus to *D. spinulifer*, differing from the latter in shorter wing cross-vein dm-m, about 1.5 times as long as distal part of M_4 and the absence of long setae on hind basitarsus. In *D. spinulifer* male, cross-vein dm-m is 2.2 times as long as distal part of M_4 ; hind basitarsus bears three long light posterodorsal setae at base, nearly half as long as basitarsus; podomere ratios are also different.

Description. Male (Fig. 11). Length (mm): body 6.5, antenna 1.3, wing 6.9/2.2. Head (Fig. 12): greenish black, weakly pollinose; clypeus shining, 1/3 as wide as head, 2 times as wide as high; face shining, 0.8 times as wide as clypeus, 1.6 times as wide as height of postpedicel; ocellar and vertical bristles strong; postvertical bristle slightly longer than upper postocular bristle; about 9 upper postocular setae black, strong, finer and whitish below; ventral 1/2 of postcranium clothed with many long white hairs; antenna (Fig. 13) mostly black, scape brownish ventrally, glabrous, vase-like; pedicel with ring of short setae; postpedicel slightly higher than long, rounded distally, with short hairs, with dorsoapical simple arista-like stylus; basal segment of stylus thickened; length (mm) of scape, pedicel, postpedicel, arista-like stylus (aristomeres 1 and 2), 0.14 : 0.08 : 0.15 : 0.14 : 0.81; palpus ovate, 1.5 times as long as wide, 1/3 as long as eye height, slightly dilated at middle; palpus orange yellow, shining white, bearing sparse black hairs; proboscis moderately large, brown.

Thorax: greenish black, with grey pollinosity; mesonotum with pair of blackish longitudinal stripes; acrostichals absent; 6–7 pairs of dorsocentrals; 3 humeral setae, 1 posthumeral, 2 notopleurals, 1 sutural, 1 postsutural, 1 supra-alar, 1 postalar; scutellum with 2 pairs of strong scutellars; proepisternum with 7–8 white hairs on its upper portion and 7–8 white setae on its lower portion; scutellum about 2 times wider than long; postscutellum 2.5 times as long as scutellum.

Legs: rather long, black, with black major setae; fore coxa on anterior surface with short white hairs, with 6 short black apical setae; fore femur simple, moderately thick in basal half, without remarkable setation, with 3 short posteroventral subapical setae, shorter than femur height; fore tibia (Fig. 14) slightly thickened, bearing 3 anterodorsal, 2 posterodorsal bristles in basal 1/3, 1 strong dorsal bristle at 2/3, 2 ventral rows of short erect black setae, 1 short apical seta; fore basitarsus long, covered with semi-erect black setulae, with ventral row of about 20 very short blunt setae in middle half (Fig. 15); tarsomeres 2–4 simple, bearing semi-erect black setulae, ventrally bare; tarsomere 4 with pair of apicoventral setae; tarsomere 5 elongated; pulvilli reduced, empodium very short, claws about 1/3 as long as tarsomere 5; mid coxa bearing short and long white hairs; mid femur simple, with row of about 10 stiff erect ventral hairs in distal half, with few ventral white hairs right behind middle, with all hairs at most as long as femur height; mid tibia straight, with 3 anterodorsal and 2 posterodorsal bristles and 5 short apical setae; mid tarsus slender, simple; tarsomere 4 with pair of apicoventral setae; tarsomere 5 with small claws, reduced pulvilli and empodium; hind coxa bearing few short white hairs laterally and 1 short black seta at apex; hind femur long and simple, with group of about 10 white hairs at base and 5 anteroventral bristles in distal half, with hairs and bristles about as long as femur height; hind tibia slender, bearing 3–4 anterodorsal and 3–4 posterodorsal bristles and 5 short apical setae, short setae on ventral surface; hind tarsus slender and simple; tarsomere 4 with pair of apicoventral setae; tarsomere 5 with small claws, reduced pulvilli and empodium. Femur, tibia and tarsomere (from first to fifth) length (mm): fore leg: 1.65 : 1.67 : 0.95 : 0.53 : 0.36 : 0.21 : 0.25; mid leg: 2.42 : 2.72 : 1.46 : 0.58 : 0.35 : 0.21 : 0.27; hind leg: 3.05 : 3.14 : 1.27 : 0.79 : 0.49 : 0.23 : 0.25.

Wing (Fig. 11): long and narrow, evenly greyish, with black veins; Sc developed; R_{2+3} and R_{4+5} weakly convex anteriorly, almost parallel in middle half of wing, then divergent distally; R_{4+5} and M_{1+2} almost parallel at wing apex; M_{1+2} weakly convex; ratio of

part of costa between R_{2+3} and R_{4+5} to this between R_{4+5} and M_{1+2} , 0.72 : 0.53; ratio of cross-vein dm-m to distal part of M_4 , 0.79 : 0.51; dm-m almost perpendicular to longitudinal wing axis; calypter brownish, with white cilia; halter yellow.

Abdomen (Fig. 16): with concave dorsal side, shining blackish blue, with short black setae; terga with black hairs; sterna 2–4 each with groups of strong brown setae; sternum 5 divided into 2 sclerites, each with distal process (Fig. 18); tergum 6 small, shortly setose; tergum 7 reduced to semicircular arc; segment 8 large, covered with brown hairs; hypopygium black, moderately large, with black appendages; hypandrium (Fig. 19) short and thick, bilobed at apex; phallus simple; epandrial lobe (Fig. 19) flat and broad, subquadrate, irregularly shaped, setose ventrally; surstylus (Fig. 20) small, hidden under epandrial lobe, with few setae; cercus (Fig. 17) black, 3/4 length of epandrium, elongate-triangular, with long yellow setae.

Female unknown.

Distribution. South Ossetia.

Etymology. The species is named after the Republic of South Ossetia, where the types have been collected.

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